

PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *The article examines the problem of similarities and differences of paremiological units, among which are proverbs, phraseological units, aphorisms, parables, fairy tales, etc. The paremiological units of the language have only their own characteristics, properties, which make it possible to distinguish them as independent varieties of paremias.*

Key words: *paremia, paremiological unit, proverb, saying, idiom, aphorism, parable, fable, fairy tale.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada paremiologik birliklarning o‘xshashliklari va farqlari muammosi ko‘rib chiqiladi, ular orasida maqollar, matallar, frazeologik birliklar, aforizmlar, masallar, ertaklar, va boshqalar mavjud. Tilning paremiologik birliklari faqat o‘ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega bo‘lib, ularni paremiyalarning mustaqil shakllari sifatida ajratishga imkon beradi.*

Калит сўзлар: *паремия, паремиологик бирлик, мақол, матал, фразеологизм, афоризм, ривоят, масал, эртак.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматривается проблема сходства и различия паремиологических единиц, среди которых пословицы, поговорки, фразеологизмы, афоризмы, притчи, сказки, басни и др. Паремиологические единицы языка обладают лишь специфическими свойствами, особенностями позволяющими выделять их в самостоятельные разновидности паремий.*

Ключевые слова: *паремия, паремиологическая единица, пословица, поговорка, фразеологизм, афоризм, притча, басня, сказка.*

The paremiological units of language, as an object and subject of scientific research, have a multifaceted character, which in their characteristic features finds expression in metaphors, imagery, allegoricity, emotional saturation, aphorisms. Problems of paremiology-teachings about paremias was carried out by -G. L. Permyakov, S. D. Mastepanov, V. M. Makienka, M. A. Cherkassky and others .In modern linguistics, to refer to the above paremiological units, they used the term paremia. Initially, the word paremia, According to V. I. Dahl's dictionary, it is a special church term that means "a passage read in the Orthodox Church during prayer, which includes prophecy or doctrine, morality from the Old Testament book." Currently, paremia is understood in two ways: narrow and wide. In a narrow sense, paremia is a proverb; a statement, dictation, judgment that refers to a proverb. In the broader sense of paremia, "a short figuratively stable statement (often used figuratively), structured syntactically as a simple or complex sentence (which can sometimes consist of several sentences), reflects a generalized formally enshrined situation raised to the formula, based on important truth, instruction, rules or principles of behavior, moral laws, life experience" [Katsyuba, 2013, p.67].

In this article, paremia refers to a short text made up of one or more sentences with a certain syntactic structure, emotionally and expressively saturated, capable of providing an aesthetic effect to the listener: "paremias are one of the subsystems of the language at the syntactic level, presented in the form of a complete or unfinished sentence, with compactness and rhythm. They are characterized by stability in the language and reproducibility in speech, partial or complete revision, as well as semantic polysemy. They are well-known, widely used by people, used for didactic purposes, are units of conscious choice depending on the speech situation, making them pragmatically ambiguous" [Matveeva, Seregina, 2009, p.178].

The number of paremiological units in linguistic literature includes proverbs, sayings, phraseological units, aphorisms, parables, fables, fairy tales, etc. Each of the paremiological units, against the background of common features with other awards, has a set of features, properties and features characteristic only of it, which allows it to

be distinguished as an independent variety of paremias. One of such paremiological units is considered to be a proverb, which, unlike phraseological units, represents characteristic signs of situations or relationships between things, and unlike aphorisms is the work of the whole people, not a specific author, and refers to works of folklore. A specific feature of the proverb is that it contains advice, edification, moralizing and has two content plans: direct and figurative.

The presence of both direct and figurative content plans in a proverb serves as the main criterion for distinguishing it from a proverb that has only a direct plan, i.e. conveys only the direct meaning of the content of the utterance, and according to the degree of cliché is an open, syntactically articulated sentence.

Paremiological units include:

- phraseological units, which in contrast of , for example, proverbs, express a concept, not a judgment and are expressed by a stable phrase, the components of which have completely or partially lost their semantic independence, phraseological units are characterized by vivid expressiveness, emotionality, expressiveness and evaluativeness;

- short expressions of an imperative type are called Maxims;
- riddles involving the listener finding the answer to the available premises;
- aphorisms that are bookish in origin and in their main functions are similar to proverbs, as they have an edifying character;

The totality of all paremiological units is that they all serve as "combat units of the language", reflecting the centuries-old experience of the people, its life and traditions, way of life, wisdom accumulated over the centuries.

Paremiological units accumulate national culture, expressing stereotypes of national consciousness. Thus, the paremiological units of the language include proverbs, sayings, phraseological units, riddles, maxims, aphorisms, etc., which have common and specific features that make it possible to consider them as special types of paremia.

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